

Quantification of ecosystem services provided by vultures supported by the LIFE SUPport project (Kvarner Islands, Croatia)

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1. Summary

- This report provides a quantification and valuation of selected ecosystem services provided by the population of Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands, Croatia, which is recovering following implementation of conservation measures including those undertaken by the LIFE SUPport project.
- The population of Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands, Croatia interacts with the local environment and human activities contributing to the provision of ecosystem services and human wellbeing. The regulating and cultural services provided by vultures include:
 - The consumption of livestock carcasses, which has value in terms of the avoided disposal costs. The beneficiaries of this service are livestock farmers and the State, which would otherwise incur these costs.
 - The avoided greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from transporting and incinerating carcasses. This is a global benefit, in terms of reduced climate change damages worldwide.
 - The sanitation service whereby the consumption of carcasses reduces the accumulation and transmission of toxins and pathogens to other animals including humans. The beneficiaries of this service are livestock farmers and the Croatian general public.
 - Nature based tourism (ecotourism) in the form of vulture watching, which has value in terms of revenue to the tourism sector and the enjoyment attained by tourists.
 - The value that the Croatian public place on the continued existence of vultures on the Kvarner Islands irrespective of any current or future use.
- The current population of Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands is estimated to be 152 breeding pairs, which corresponds to approximately 399 individuals including non-breeders.
- The values of ecosystem services provided by these vultures in 2024 are estimated to be EUR 14,000 in avoided carcass disposal costs, EUR 3,700 in avoided GHG emissions, EUR 375,000 in direct expenditure on vulture related ecotourism, and EUR 6,464,000 in indirect expenditure on tourist services.

- These value estimates provide a first indication of the importance of vultures on the Kvarner Islands to human activities and wellbeing. It should be noted, however, that this analysis encompasses only a subset of the ecosystem services provided by these vultures. Potential avenues for further research include the estimation of existence values held by the Croatian public for increased vulture populations and the estimation of the return on investment in conservation activities.

Vulture ecosystem services: linking vultures on the Kvarner Islands with ecosystem services, values and beneficiaries.

2. Abstract

The population of Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands of Croatia, which is recovering following implementation of conservation measures including those undertaken by the LIFE SUPport project, provide a number of ecosystem services that benefit people including the consumption of livestock carcasses, which reduces the direct financial costs and the greenhouse gas emissions associated with carcass disposal, and the contribution to ecotourism in the form of vulture watching. This report provides a quantification and valuation of these ecosystem services. The 2024 population of Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands is estimated to be 152 breeding pairs, which corresponds to

approximately 399 individuals including non-breeders. The values provided by these vultures in 2024 are estimated to be EUR 14,000 in avoided carcass disposal costs, EUR 3,700 in avoided GHG emissions, EUR 375,000 in direct expenditure on vulture related ecotourism, and EUR 6,464,000 in indirect expenditure on tourist services. These value estimates provide a first indication of the importance of vultures on the Kvarner Islands to human activities and wellbeing. To support conservation decision making, future analyses should cover other relevant ecosystem services provided by vultures for which there is currently no data available for their assessment, and estimation of the return on conservation investments relative to the costs.

3. Introduction

Vultures on the Kvarner Islands provide a number of ecosystem services that benefit people including the consumption of livestock carcasses, which reduces the direct financial costs and the greenhouse gas emissions associated with carcass disposal, and the contribution to ecotourism in the form of vulture watching. This report provides a quantification and valuation of these ecosystem services provided by the population of Griffon Vultures (*Gyps fulvus*) on the Kvarner Islands, which is recovering following implementation of conservation measures including those undertaken by the LIFE SUPport project.

Ecosystem Services

The concept of ecosystem services provides a useful framework to identify the importance of the natural environment, including wild animal species, to humans. The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA, 2005) defines ecosystem services as benefits that ecosystems provide for people while The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB, 2010) describes these services as the direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to human well-being. Put most simply, Ecosystem Services are the variety of benefits that people obtain from the environment.

Ecosystems contribute to human wellbeing in a wide variety of ways and the processes by which ecosystems provide benefits to people has been described as an “ecosystem services cascade” in which bio-physical structures and processes (“ecosystem functions”) can deliver inputs (ecosystem services) to the production of goods and services that contribute to the wellbeing of people (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ecosystem services “cascade”. Adapted from Haines-Young and Potschin (2010).

The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA, 2005) classification of ecosystem services introduced the following four categories of services:

- Provisioning services are the “products obtained from ecosystems”. Examples include food, timber and fuel.
- Regulating services are the “benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes”. Examples include water flow regulation, carbon sequestration and protection from storms.
- Cultural services are the “non-material benefits people obtain from ecosystems through spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, reflection, recreation, and aesthetic experiences”.
- Supporting services “are necessary for the production of all other ecosystem services”. Examples include nutrient cycling, soil formation and primary production.

The inclusion of supporting services in the classification can potentially lead to the double counting of values, since the ecosystem contribution is counted as both an intermediate and final service, and more recent classification systems have therefore omitted such “intermediate services” (e.g. Common International Classification of Ecosystem services – CICES; and the SEEA Ecosystem Accounting reference list).

Total Economic Value

The concept of Total Economic Value (TEV) is used to describe the comprehensive set of utilitarian values derived from an ecosystem or natural resource (Pearce and Turner, 1990). The concept is useful for identifying the different types of value that may be derived from an ecosystem or species population. TEV comprises of “use values” and “non-use values”. Use values are the benefits that are derived from some physical use of the resource. “Direct use values” may derive from on-site extraction of resources (e.g. meat) or non-consumptive activities (e.g. nature-based tourism). “Indirect use values” are derived from off-site services or other processes that are impacted by the resource (e.g. disposal of carcasses; control of disease). “Option value” is the value that people place on maintaining the option to use a resource in the future (e.g. the option to develop ecotourism). “Non-use values” are derived from the knowledge that an ecosystem or species population is maintained without regard to any current or future personal use. “Non-use values” may be related to altruism (maintaining a species population for use by others), bequest (for future generations) and existence (preservation unrelated to any use) motivations. The constituent values of TEV are represented in Figure 2. It should be noted that the “total” in Total Economic Value refers to the *inclusion of all components* of value rather than the sum of all value derived from a resource.

Figure 2: Components of Total Economic Value derived from vultures.

The classification of different types of economic value within the concept of TEV is complementary to the classification of ecosystem services. Figure 3 sets out the correspondence between categories of ecosystem service and components of TEV.

Figure 3: Correspondence between ecosystem services and components of TEV with examples related to vultures.

LIFE SUPport project

The LIFE SUPport project aims to improve breeding and survival conditions for the last remaining population of Griffon Vultures in the Kvarner Islands, Croatia. By tackling the most important threats on their breeding grounds, the current population of 152 Griffon Vulture pairs will continue to survive and possibly increase in number, which is an important first step for the species to re-colonize their historical breeding ranges on the Croatian mainland and connect to other populations in the Alps and Balkans. The most important threats targeted by this project are nest disturbance, lack of food, poisoning and electrocution. The main objectives of the project are:

- Reducing nesting mortality by minimizing nest disturbance and by improving the rescue and rehabilitation operations of the Beli Rescue Centre for Griffon Vultures.
- Increasing food availability for vultures by improving and expanding the existing network of managed feeding stations and by increasing natural feeding opportunities.
- Prevention of poisoning events by exploring best preventive measures to avoid the use of poisoned baits, by promoting the use of lead-free ammunition and by capacity building of relevant enforcement agencies for combating illegal wildlife poisoning.
- Reducing mortality arising from electrocution by applying appropriate mitigation measures on the most important electrocution hotspots.
- Promoting Griffon Vultures and raising awareness of their threats and needs to local stakeholders, the wider public and government bodies.

Objectives

The overall objective of this study is to assess the contribution of Griffon Vultures in the study area to ecosystem services. The specific objectives are to:

1. Develop a conceptual model of how the vulture population interacts with the local environment and human activities to contribute to the provision of ecosystem services and human wellbeing. This conceptual framework is in line with the guidance for assessing ecosystems and their services in LIFE projects (LIFE, 2021).
2. Quantify in biophysical and monetary terms the following ecosystem services provided by Griffon Vultures in the study area:
 - a. Livestock carcass consumption resulting in reduced costs to farmers and public authorities.
 - b. Climate regulation by reducing greenhouse gas emissions associated with collection and transportation of carcasses.
 - c. Ecotourism associated with vulture populations.

4. Study area and Vulture population

The LIFE SUPport project is implemented on the islands of Cres, Krk and Rab, the largest of the Kvarner Islands. The entire breeding population of Griffon Vultures in Croatia is restricted to four of the Kvarner islands: Cres, Krk, Prvić and Plavnik, and also to neighboring parts of Mt. Učka, where they started to breed in recent years. Griffon Vultures breed on cliffs directly above the sea, which is a rare feature, not observed in many other countries of its breeding range.

Figure 4. Kvarner Islands, Croatia

Estimates for the population of Griffon Vultures in the study area at the start of the LIFE project and over time with and without conservation activities are based on the expert opinions of project partners. The numbers of Griffon Vultures in the study area before the start of the LIFE project is estimated to be 121 breeding pairs in 2021, which is assumed to correspond to 318 individuals including non-breeders.

Predicting how vulture populations may change in the future entails uncertainty but potentially provides a basis to conduct an exploratory scenario analysis and estimate the benefits of conservation action. We forecast how vulture populations may change under a scenario ‘with conservation’ and under a scenario ‘without conservation’.

The estimated total populations of Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands over the period 2021-2034, with and without conservation action, are represented in Figure 5. With conservation activities in place, the current (2024) population is estimated to be 152 breeding pairs (approximately 399 individuals), which is expected to increase to 175 breeding pairs (approximately 460 individuals) by the end of the LIFE project (2028) and continue to increase to approximately 195 breeding pairs (approximately 599 individuals) in 2034. Without any conservation efforts over the same time period, it is estimated that the population would decline to 60 breeding pairs (approximately 158 individuals).

Figure 5. Estimated population of Griffon Vultures on Kvarner Islands with and without conservation (2021-2034).

5. Conceptual model for vulture valuation in Croatia

To develop a conceptual model for the valuation of vultures on the Kvarner Islands, we build on the ecosystem services cascade (Figure 1; Haines-Young and Potschin, 2010) and total economic valuation frameworks (Figure 2; Pearce and Turner, 1990). Furthermore, a literature review was used to obtain information on the ecosystem services provided by vultures (see Appendix 1).

In the context of the Kvarner Islands, vultures provide both regulating and cultural services. Provisioning services are not relevant in this context because vultures' parts are not used or consumed in Croatia (for examples elsewhere see Daboné et al., 2023).

Regulating services include the consumption of livestock carcasses, which has value both in terms of the avoided disposal costs and the avoided greenhouse gas emissions from transporting and incinerating carcasses. The avoided disposal costs are a benefit to livestock farmers and the State, which would otherwise incur these costs. The avoided costs of greenhouse gas emissions is a global benefit, in terms of reduced climate change damages worldwide. A second regulating service that is potentially relevant in the context of the Kvarner Islands is the sanitation service whereby the consumption of carcasses reduces the accumulation and transmission of toxins and pathogens to other animals including humans. This service, however, is not assessed in the present study (indicated by the lighter shading in Figure 6).

Regarding cultural services, vultures provide a contribution to nature-based tourism, which has value in terms of revenue to the tourism sector (and the general economy) and the enjoyment attained by tourists. A second relevant cultural service is the value that the Croatian public place on the continued existence of vultures on the Kvarner Islands irrespective of any current or future use. Such non-use values have been shown to be substantial for vulture populations in other countries (e.g., Brander et al., 2024) and are likely to also be relevant in the Croatian context.

The conceptual framework identifies the different groups of beneficiaries that obtain value from vultures on the Kvarner Islands. These include livestock farmers, the Croatian general public, the global public, the tourism sector and tourists.

Figure 6: Conceptual framework linking vultures on the Kvarner Islands with ecosystem services, values and beneficiaries. Lighter shaded ecosystem services and values indicate that these are relevant in the context of the Kvarner Islands but not included in the assessment presented in this report.

6. Quantification and valuation of ecosystem services

6.1 Reduced financial cost of livestock carcass disposal

The role of vultures in consuming livestock carcasses on the Kvarner Islands is estimated using information on the vulture population, daily food requirement, the proportion of vultures' diet from livestock, and the proportion of a carcass that is soft tissue consumed by vultures.

The value of this ecosystem service is estimated as the avoided costs of carcass collection and disposal:

1. The annual consumption of livestock carcasses by Griffon Vultures is computed by multiplying the vulture population by the daily food requirement of an adult Griffon Vulture (0.52 kg/day;

Lopez and Merono, 2019; Santos et al., 2024) by 365 days and by the proportion of diet derived from livestock (68.3%; Arrondo et al., 2023).¹²

2. The live weight of livestock carcasses consumed by vultures is computed by multiplying the quantity estimated in step 1 by the inverse proportion of soft tissue in a carcass (73%; Jarvis et al., 1974).³
3. This quantity of food required by the Griffon Vulture population exceeds the quantity of livestock carcasses available and so the food requirement is met by transporting livestock carcasses to two feeding stations, one in Učka Nature Park and the other at Strganac on Cres island (BIOM, 2024). Annual quantities of food delivered to each site are approximately 10,000kg to Učka Nature Park (BIOM, 2024) and 34,000 kg to Strganac. Subtracting these quantities from the estimated live weight of livestock carcasses consumed (step 2) provides an estimate of the weight of livestock carcasses that would otherwise need to be collected and disposed of.⁴⁵
4. The avoided cost of carcass collection and disposal per kg is computed using information on the quantity and cost of transporting livestock carcasses to the feeding station on Cres from the mainland. In 2024 this amounted to 33,757 kg at a cost of EUR 17,470, which gives a cost per kg of EUR/kg 0.52.⁶
5. The estimated weight of livestock carcasses on the Kvarner islands that are consumed by vultures (step 3) is multiplied by the cost of collection and disposal (step 4) to estimate the annual avoided costs attributable to this ecosystem service.⁷

The estimated quantities and values of livestock carcass disposal by Griffon Vultures in 2024 are provided in Table 1. The quantity of livestock carcasses consumed by vultures that would otherwise require collection, transportation and disposal is estimated to be almost 13 tonnes and the annual avoided disposal costs are estimated to be almost EUR 6,600. These estimates are low because of the low number of livestock kept on the Kvarner islands.

¹ We note that the proportion of vulture diet derived from livestock as opposed to wild animals is highly spatially variable and likely to be lower in remote areas (Arrondo et al., 2023).

² Annual consumption of livestock carcasses by one Griffon vulture = $0.52 \times 365 \times 0.685 = 130$ kg/year

³ Live weight of livestock carcasses consumed by one Griffon Vulture per year = $130 \times (1 - 0.73) = 178$ kg/year.
Total live weight of livestock carcasses consumed by the population of Griffon Vultures in 2021 = $178 \times 318 = 70,941$ kg/year.

⁴ This estimate is validated by comparison with the estimated quantity of livestock carcass availability on the Kvarner islands derived from data on livestock numbers and mortality rates (BIOM, 2024).

⁵ Weight of livestock carcasses consumed that would otherwise need to be collected and disposed of (i.e., net of carcasses transported to feeding stations) = $70,941 - 43,757 = 27,184$ kg/year.

⁶ Alternatively, using the total quantity (19,188 kg) and cost (EUR 13,200) in 2023, would give a slightly higher unit cost of EUR/kg 0.69.

⁷ Annual avoided costs of livestock collection and disposal = $27,184 \times 0.52 = 14,068$ EUR/year.

Table 1. Avoided quantities and costs of carcass collection and disposal by Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands (2024 price level).

Live weight of carcasses (kg)	27,184
Avoided disposal costs (EUR)	14,068

6.2 Reduced greenhouse gas emissions

The reduced emission of greenhouse gases (GHG) attributable to the role of vultures in consuming livestock carcasses is estimated using information on the quantity of livestock carcasses that would otherwise need to be collected and disposed of (see quantification in preceding section) and the emissions associated with transportation of carcasses. The value of this ecosystem service is measured as the avoided damage costs of climate change using estimates of the social cost of carbon (SCC).

1. The estimated weight of livestock carcasses that are consumed by vultures and would otherwise need to be collected and disposed of by people is described in the preceding section.
2. The quantity of GHG emissions per tonne of collected livestock carcass is obtained from a study for Sardinia (Santangeli et al., 2024), which is similar in terms of the need for transportation of carcasses by ferry for disposal on the mainland. Dividing the estimates provided in that study for the annual quantity of GHG emissions associated with carcass collection and disposal (96.07 tonnes CO₂-equivalent) by the annual quantity of carcasses collected (95.70 tonnes) gives a rate of emissions of 1 tonne CO₂-equivalent per tonne of carcasses.⁸
3. The quantity of avoided GHG emissions per year is estimated by multiplying the quantity of livestock carcasses on the Kvarner islands that are consumed by vultures by the rate of GHG emissions (step 2).
4. The avoided climate change damage costs attributable to the reduced GHG emissions is computed by multiplying the quantity of reduced emissions (step 3) by the social cost of carbon (SCC). The SCC is the monetary value of damages caused by emitting one additional tonne of CO₂ in a given year and therefore also represents the value of damages avoided for a small reduction in emissions. The estimated SCC for emissions 2024 provided by the US EPA (2023) were converted from 2020 to 2024 price level using GDP deflator data from the World Bank

⁸ This rate of emissions is slightly higher than the rate estimated for carcass disposal on Sardinia by Santangeli et al. (2024).

(2024) and from USD to EUR using a market exchange rate of 0.95 (Oanda, 2024). The SCC for (avoided) emissions in 2024 is EUR 149/t CO₂.

The estimated quantities and values of avoided greenhouse gas emissions attributable to Griffon Vultures in 2024 are provided in Table 2. The total quantity of avoided GHG emissions attributable to vultures on the Kvarner Islands is estimated to be tCO₂ 13, with a value in terms of avoided climate change damage costs of over EUR 1,700. These estimates are low because of the low number of livestock kept on the Kvarner islands.

Table 2. Avoided quantities and costs of GHG emissions by Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands in 2024 (2024 price level).

Avoided GHG emissions (tCO ₂)	27
Avoided GHG emissions (EUR)	3,714

6.3 Ecotourism

Ecotourism is travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well-being of local people. In many cases, ecotourism generates financial and public support for conservation activities (Buckley et al., 2016). In the context of this study, the presence of vultures in the landscape has the potential to attract bird watchers and generate revenues in the local economy for tours and other tourism services.

We assess the value of Griffon Vultures to ecotourism on the Kvarner Islands through two activities: 1. Visits to the Beli visitor centre and rescue centre for Griffon Vultures⁹ on Cres; 2. Boat tours of Plavnik Island to see vulture breeding sites.

The number of visitors per year to the Beli centre during the period 2016-2024 is represented in Figure 7. It shows that the number of visitors is increasing over time, with the exception of 2020-2021 due to the Covid-19 pandemic and reached 12,000 visitors in 2024. The revenue from entrance tickets for the centre was EUR 45,000.

Boat tours of Plavnik island are provided by a number of operators departing from Cres, Krk and ports on the mainland. The tours provide the opportunity for visitors to view Griffon Vulture breeding sites, other fauna (e.g., other birds, dolphins, coral) and cultural heritage on the island. The number of tourists

⁹ <https://belivisitorcentre.eu/en/>

that took a boat tour of Plavnik Island in 2024 is estimated to be 11,000. The average price of a boat tour is EUR 30 and the estimated total expenditure on tours in 2024 is EUR 330,000.

In addition to direct expenditure by tourists on entrance to the Beli centre and boat tours of Plavnik Island, we also consider the value of indirect expenditure on tourist services such as accommodation, food and transportation. Average tourist daily expenditure per private trip with overnight stay in Croatia amounted to EUR 281 (Croatian Bureau of Statistics, 2024). Attributing one day per visit to the Beli centre or boat tour of Plavnik Island, we estimate the value of expenditure on associated tourist services to be EUR 6,464,000.

Figure 7. Number of visitors to the Beli visitor centre 2016-2024.

Table 3. Direct and indirect tourist expenditure on culture related activities in 2024 (Euros/year)

Beli Centre	45,000
Plavnik Island boat tours	330,000
Indirect tourist expenditure	6,464,000

7. Discussion and conclusions

In this section we provide a brief summary and discussion of the findings and identify potential avenues for further research into vulture ecosystem services and their values in the study area.

Summary and discussion of findings

The analysis presented in this report focuses on three ecosystem services provided by Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands, namely the avoided costs of livestock carcass disposal, reduced greenhouse gas emissions associated with carcass transportation, and the contribution to ecotourism by attracting visitors that want to view vultures in the wild.

The current (2024) population of Griffon Vultures on the Kvarner Islands are estimated to be 152 breeding pairs, which corresponds to approximately 399 individuals including non-breeders. The values of the ecosystem services provided by these vultures in 2024 is estimated to be EUR 14,000 in avoided carcass disposal costs, EUR 3,700 in avoided GHG emissions, EUR 375,000 in direct expenditure on vulture related ecotourism, and EUR 6,464,000 in indirect expenditure on tourist services.

The contribution of vultures to ecotourism delivers substantial economic value, the beneficiaries of which are the Beli centre, boat tour operators, the broader tourist sector that provides accommodation and other services, and the tourists themselves. The relatively low value of regulating services is due to both the limited number of vultures and the limited number of livestock on the Kvarner Islands. The food requirements of the current vulture population already exceed the availability of livestock carcasses, which necessitates the transportation of livestock carcasses from the mainland to the feeding station on Cres. This transportation of carcasses, and the associated GHG emissions, is in effect a cost of maintaining the vulture population. The cost of transporting sufficient quantities of livestock carcasses to the feeding stations will rise over time with the growing vulture population and we estimate that the cost will reach approximately EUR 90,000 per year in 2034.¹⁰ It is likely, however, that the lack of availability of food for vultures is not entirely due to a lack of livestock carcasses on the Kvarner Islands but partly due to management practices that require farmers to report and send away dead animals, and that many of the animals that die are not accessible to vultures (e.g., inside woods). Making the livestock carcasses on the Kvarner Islands available to vultures would therefore potentially reduce the costs and emissions associated with supplying the feeding stations from the mainland.

¹⁰ Based on the estimated vulture population of 513 individuals in 2034.

Avenues for future research to quantify ecosystem services provided by vultures

The assessment presented in this report has a number of limitations that could potentially be addressed in future research including:

- There are several uncertainties regarding the data and parameters used in the analysis. To the largest extent possible, we have used information pertaining directly to the study site, but several uncertainties remain.
- The estimated values are for the ecosystem services provided by the current population of vultures. In addition, it would be informative for conservation planning to understand how these values might change over time under scenarios that describe alternative conservation efforts and outcomes. The additional value of ecosystem services delivered by a larger vulture population can be interpreted as the benefits of successful conservation. Section 4 describes two alternative scenarios for the vulture population on the Kvarner Islands with and without conservation activities but to assess the change in ecosystem services requires understanding of how this translates into ecosystem service provision. In the case of livestock carcass disposal, there is limited scope to expand this service given the limited number of livestock and the need to transport additional food for vultures from the mainland. There may be greater scope for expanding vulture related ecotourism across the Kvarner Islands and future research could explore this potential.
- Due to the lack of understanding on how the numbers of ecotourism visits in the study area would increase with higher numbers of vultures, we do not estimate how the value of this ecosystem service might develop over time as the vulture population increases. Future research could therefore aim to provide greater understanding of the role of vultures for ecotourism through surveys of potential visitors. Such surveys could try to quantify the proportion of visitors that would be interested in viewing vultures on the Kvarner Islands, their willingness to pay per visit, and how this might change with increasing vulture populations.
- The assessment addresses a sub-set of three ecosystem services provided by vultures on the Kvarner Islands. Other services are relevant in the Croatian context (see Figure 6) and potentially of high importance. Future research could therefore attempt to quantify and value these ecosystem services. In particular, the non-use (existence and bequest) values that people in Croatia place on increased vulture populations could be assessed using stated preference methods. This would involve conducting a survey of the general public to ask questions on willingness to pay for increasing the population and distribution of vultures on the Kvarner islands and mainland.

- The assessment provides a partial estimate of the benefits of vulture conservation. The analysis could be expanded to provide a more comprehensive estimate of conservation benefits and potentially extend to a Cost-Benefit Analysis to evaluate the return on conservation investments. This would provide conservation partners and donors with information on the extent to which investments deliver positive returns.

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10. Appendix 1: Literature review on ecosystem services provided by vultures

A literature review is used to obtain information on the ecosystem services provided by vultures. It builds on existing reviews and involves a search of literature databases to provide an overview of the literature on ecosystem services derived from vultures and the economic value of these services. The review includes peer reviewed journal articles, working papers and research reports, academic dissertations and theses, NGO publications, and government reports.

The literature search was conducted using a variety of sources to ensure a comprehensive collection of studies was obtained. Conventional online literature tools and libraries such as Google Scholar, Scopus, ResearchGate, Mendeley, and institutional libraries were utilized to gather relevant published literature. Reports and studies that cited a large number of sources were used as a source of references, which helped to identify additional relevant literature. Combinations of search terms were used to capture the diverse terminology used in the field.

The results of the literature review are summarised in Table A1, which lists ecosystem services provided by vultures, provides a brief description of the service, and cites relevant publications.

In addition to identifying key ecosystem services provided by vultures, the literature review is used to obtain relevant existing vulture valuation studies, the results of which may potentially be transferred or scaled up to the European context. The collected valuation studies may also provide guidance and recommendations for future valuations of vultures.

From the literature review, we identified 12 studies that estimate the economic value of vulture ecosystem services. These studies are summarised in Table A2. The geographic coverage of these studies is broad, including locations in Europe, Asia, North and South America, and Southern Africa.

Regarding the ecosystem services that have been valued in the literature, six studies estimate values for carcass and waste disposal (Margalida and Colomer, 2012; Ishwar et al., 2016; Grilli et al., 2019; Phipps and Vogiatzakis, 2020; Brander et al., 2024; Santangeli et al., 2024), four for ecotourism (Becker et al.,

2005; García-Jiménez et al., 2021; Becker et al., 2010; Brander et al., 2024), four for existence values (Becker et al., 2010; Baral et al., 2007; Zambrano-Monserrate, 2020; Brander et al., 2024), and two for the control of pests (and in consequence the control of diseases spread by feral dogs – Markandya et al., 2008; Berlinguer et al., 2021). The single valuation study for provisioning services supplied by vultures estimates the value of vulture parts used in belief-based use in Southern Africa (Brander et al., 2024).

The application of valuation methods corresponds closely to the ecosystem services that are valued. The valuation of waste disposal used the replacement cost method, with the underlying assumption that livestock carcasses disposed of by vultures would need to be replaced by human-made processing, such as collection, burial or incineration. This valuation method can provide lower bound estimates of the value of an ecosystem service, but only if the following conditions are met: (1) the human-made disposal process provides the same level of service as the ecosystem being replaced; (2) the human-made process should be the least-cost alternative; and (3) there should be substantial evidence that the service delivered by the infrastructure would be demanded by society if it were provided at cost (Shabman and Batie, 1978). In practice, most applications of the replacement cost method do not meet these conditions and tend to greatly over-estimate the value of ecosystem services (Barbier, 2016). This is because the cost of infrastructure is not a good proxy of the benefits that it delivers (benefits can be lower than costs if the infrastructure is redundant); and the selected replacement infrastructures/processes used in many studies are not the least-cost alternative. The replacement cost method is widely used due to its relative convenience (costs of human-made infrastructure are widely available) (World Bank, 2016) but when used inappropriately, it delivers misinformation on the value of ecosystem services.

The first study that examines the role of vultures in controlling pests (Markandya et al., 2008), estimates the value of changes in the prevalence of human health endpoints (morbidity and mortality) due to changes in the abundance of feral dogs that spread rabies using a combination of the costs of treatment and the value of a statistical life (VOSL). In this approach, the biophysical quantification of changes in pest populations in response to changes in vulture populations (controlling for other factors), and the associated changes in prevalence of disease (again controlling for other factors) presents a greater challenge than the monetary valuation of health endpoints, for which country specific data are generally available. The second study to estimate the value of this service (Berlinguer et al., 2021) applies the replacement cost method in a similar approach to the valuations of the waste disposal service.

Ecotourism associated with vultures has been valued using several methods, including the travel cost method, gross expenditure and time opportunity per trip, and the contingent valuation method. These methods measure different concepts of value derived from tourist activities. The travel cost and contingent valuation applications produce estimates of consumer surplus to tourists; whereas gross expenditure and time opportunity cost produce an estimate of exchange value. The latter approach is

likely to substantially over-estimate the value of vulture viewing since it attributes the entire cost of a trip to this single motivation.

The values that people place on the continued existence of vultures, irrespective of any current or future use, have been estimated using stated preference methods (contingent valuation and choice experiments). The contingent valuation method involves the measurement of willingness to pay (WTP) for a specified change in vulture population or conservation programme through a public survey. To date there is only one application of the discrete choice experiment method to estimate existence values for vultures (Brander et al., 2024). This stated preference method has largely superseded the contingent valuation method over the past decade and enables the estimation of WTP for changes in defined attributes of conservation (e.g. population trends, population size, species diversity, species extinctions) and subsequently the valuation of alternative conservation programmes/outcomes defined in terms of these attributes.

Table A1. Ecosystem services provided by vultures (adapted from Fitzpatrick et al., 2018; Carucci et al. 2022)

	Ecosystem service	Description of vulture ecosystem service	Reference
Provisioning services	Food from wild animals	Vultures used or traded for consumption	Saidu and Buij, 2013
	Materials from wild animals	Vulture parts used in traditional practices (medicine, healing, prophecy)	Craig et al., 2018; Mdhlano et al., 2018; Mashele et al., 2021
Regulating services	Waste disposal	Disposal of dead livestock and organic waste produced by humans	Gangoso et al., 2012; Phipps and Vogiatzakis, 2020; Buechley et al., 2022
	Sanitation service through disposal of carrion and waste	Reduced accumulation of toxins from breeding micro-organisms in carrion. In addition, pathogens are destroyed in the digestive tract of vultures.	Margalida, A., and Colomer, 2012; Ishwar et al., 2016; Donazar et al., 2016; Grilli et al., 2019; Houston and Cooper 1975; van den Heever et al. 2021; Jalihal et al., 2022; Frank and Sudarshan, 2024
	Controlling pests and invasive species	Presence of vultures reduces number of other scavengers (e.g. feral dogs, jackals, rats and hyenas) at carcasses that can be harmful to human and livestock health through disease transfer. This can also result in a reduction in human-wildlife conflict. Also reduction in invertebrate pest species that hatch their eggs in rotting meat.	Markandya et al., 2008; Ogada et al., 2012a; 2012b; Berlinguer et al., 2021; van den Heever et al. 2021; Beuchley et al., 2016; 2022; Brink, 2022; Frank and Sudarshan, 2024
	Maintenance of soil quality	Soil microbial communities associated with vultures exhibit greater phylogenetic clustering in bacterial communities.	Ganz et al., 2012
	Global climate regulation	Vultures consume livestock carcasses that would otherwise require collection, transportation and disposal.	Morales-Reyes et al., 2015; Phipps and Vogiatzakis, 2021; Plaza and Lambertucci, 2022; Santangeli et al., 2024.

	Ecosystem service	Description of vulture ecosystem service	Reference
Cultural services	Cultural significance	Role in mythology. Seeing vultures in flight is uplifting for many people. Inspiration for art, music and creativity. Part of traditional stories and expressions.	Craig et al., 2018; Jacques-Coper et al. 2019; Aguilera-Alcala et al. 2020; Daboné et al., 2022
	Nature based tourism	Viewing and photographing vultures is among the reasons for tourism visits.	Becker et al., 2005; 2010; Phipps and Vogiatzakis, 2020; García-Jiménez et al., 2021; Brander et al., 2024
	Sentinel role for identifying the location of dead animals	The presence of vultures can help livestock farmers and wildlife managers to locate dead livestock/poaching sites	Safford et al., 2019; Brander et al., 2024
	Existence and bequest values	People place value on the continued existence of vultures irrespective of any current or future use; or to ensure their existence for future generations	Baral et al., 2007; Zambrano-Monserrate, 2020;

Table A2. Economic valuations of ecosystem services provided by vultures

Ecosystem Service	Species	Valuation Method	Location	Reference
Materials from vultures used in traditional medicines	Vultures	Net factor income	Botswana, Zambia, Zimbabwe	Brander et al., 2024
Waste disposal	European vultures	Replacement cost	Europe	Margalida and Colomer, 2012
Waste disposal	Griffon vulture	Replacement cost	India	Ishwar et al., 2016
Waste disposal	Turkey Vultures	Replacement cost	North and South America	Grilli et al., 2019

Waste disposal	Vultures	Replacement cost	Botswana, Zimbabwe	Zambia,	Brander et al., 2024
Waste disposal	Griffon Vultures	Replacement cost	Sardinia, Italy		Santangeli et al., 2024
Control of disease	Vultures	Avoided damage costs to human health	Botswana, Zimbabwe	Zambia,	Brander et al., 2024
Control of pests and disease	Vultures	Treatment costs; Value of statistical life	India		Markandya et al., 2008
Control of pests	Griffon vulture	Replacement cost	Sardinia		Berlinguer et al., 2021
Sentinel role for identifying the location of dead animals	Vultures	Replacement cost	Botswana, Zimbabwe	Zambia,	Brander et al., 2024
Ecotourism	Avian scavengers	Market price; Opportunity cost	Spain		García-Jiménez et al., 2021
Ecotourism	Griffon vulture	Gross revenue	Cyprus		Phipps and Vogiatzakis, 2020
Ecotourism	Vultures	Net factor income	Botswana, Zimbabwe	Zambia,	Brander et al., 2024
Ecotourism; Existence value	Griffon vulture	Travel cost; Contingent valuation	Israel		Becker et al., 2010
Existence value	White-rumped vulture	Contingent valuation	Nepal		Baral et al., 2007
Existence value	Andean Condor	Contingent valuation	Ecuador		Zambrano-Monserrate, 2020
Existence value	Vultures	Contingent valuation; Choice experiment	Botswana, Zimbabwe	Zambia,	Brander et al., 2024

11. Appendix 2: Detailed methods on Griffon Vulture population forecast (2021-2034)

12. Appendix 3: Social Cost of Carbon

Table A2.1. Social cost of carbon 2020-2050. (EUR at 2024 price level; initial discount rate 2.5%).

Adapted from US EPA (2023).

Year	SCC (EUR/tCO ₂) 2024 price level
2020	136
2021	138
2022	142
2023	145
2024	149
2025	151
2026	155
2027	158
2028	162
2029	164
2030	168
2031	171
2032	175
2033	178
2034	180
2035	184
2036	187
2037	191
2038	194
2039	198
2040	201
2041	205

Year	SCC (EUR/tCO2) 2024 price level
2042	208
2043	212
2044	216
2045	220
2046	223
2047	227
2048	232
2049	235
2050	238

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